

Is Human Agency in Crisis?

Thoughts on New Processes of Collective Stasis

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Abstract

Humankind is confronted with multiple, interrelated environmental and societal challenges. To do something about them, I believe we need to nourish our capability to act intentionally and purposefully within complex and often hindering environments. However, highlighting this need, in this essay, I reflect on current issues that are likely to systematically diminish human agency in novel ways: the technological escalation of the attention economy; problems stemming from social media and the accessibility of the digital space; the ever-present pull of new sources of addictions; the emergence of AI; and processes of individualization and the related loneliness pandemic. I conclude with a reflection on our personal responsibility and the role of research.

1. Introduction

*“What we gonna do to wake up?
We sleep so deep, it don't matter how they shake us
If we can't face it, we can't escape it
But tonight the storms come”*

(Tunnel Vision by [Kae Tempest, 2016](#))

Probably many of us feel currently like the world is falling apart. It is easy to feel overwhelmed by the ongoing, multi-faceted and complex societal developments, the many national and global challenges humanity is confronted with, requiring some sort of substantial change. Multiple studies suggest that particularly ‘people in the west’ look more and more pessimistic into the future due to such societal challenges ([Ipsos, 2024](#); [Pew Research Center, 2025](#); [World Economic Forum, 2025](#)). We are struck, by the realization of the emergence of the many, simultaneous crises we can't escape, if we continue not to face them: the climate and environmental catastrophe, the malfunctioning of financial and economic systems and related accelerating power accumulation, looming societal disruptions due to AI, or the substantial dangers of possibly failing, self-dismantling liberal democracies, to name a few.

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What can we do?

To put it quite simply, it seems like, if we want to save our planet and our societies – our homes – we, whoever this collective we is, have to do something about it. We have to acknowledge the issues at hand and find and impersonate ways to do something about these challenges. Otherwise, we will merely react to their potentially disastrous consequences, which are partially taking place already now.

To me, these surmounting crises urge us to find our agency. It appears trivial that we can only do something about any problem, any injustice in the world, if we, or at least some of us, decide to diverge from our existing trajectories purposefully and at least really try to make change happen. This involves to not wait until the pressures become so intense and the consequences so harming, that we are basically forced out of pure necessity of present reality. It involves to anticipate, and to care, and to get out of inaction.

Throughout my years of study, I always wondered, as many other people have too, about the underlying question of this issue of inaction in the face of tremendous issues and injustices: *Why don't we do anything, if we know better?*² And looking closer, it becomes clear that there is no simple answer to this, that it is also not us collectively, who are simply not doing anything in this regard but should, because we are not all in power or all responsible for everything. Still, especially considering this background of many people worrying about the state of the world, I think we have to ask such questions on a general level over and over again, for all of us. Because I want to believe that for most people, there are, in principle, ways to try to initiate or nurture processes of change right in this regard, relating to the 'big problems' we care about.

For this, however, I think we have to understand better our individual and collective agency, meaning, *the individual or collective capability to conceive and perform intentional (or purposeful) action right within and with reference to specific spatio-temporal contexts*. In this essay, I want to reflect on why I have the feeling that it becomes harder and harder to take action, not only with regard to the mentioned crises, but also just on a very simple, individual level. This is to me basically only one kind of answer to the question of why we don't act to face the need for societal change, why it becomes increasingly difficult to act intentionally in the environments we find ourselves in.

The last three years, I had the opportunity to think much about the issue of agency, what it means or can mean to be useful, and particularly, how it relates to purposeful societal change. I believe, and have argued in a recent publication in greater detail, that the abovementioned definition of the term, as agency being about intentional

² This question may suggest, that a state of consensus regarding doing something about the 'big problems', as well as shared knowledge regarding their solutions is reached already, which we just have to enact. This implication is of course not true. What is meant with this question, is the situation, that a large majority of people of a society know about and mostly agree on certain challenges (such as the need for dealing with climate change, or the injustices of the economic system) but for some reason fail to do something about them. This 'fail to do something' can entail not reaching a consensus regarding a pathway, not reaching a collective action due to a lack of individual or collective agency, to really face the challenge which is agreed upon.

(in the sense of purposeful and deliberate) action, opposed to habitual, routine-governed, subconscious behaviour, is highly useful for understanding change (Schürer, 2025). However, I want to mention that, as is common with such broad and fundamental terms, intense discussions can (and should) be had over what such a term as agency means or ought to mean, with all its underlying ontological or epistemic assumptions.³

However, I want to take a shortcut here, and not delve into these intricacies, and more take this heuristic distinction of agency and action in contrast to (subconscious) behaviour, routine or habit, as a given. Many argue rightly so that we have to change our very routines and habits, change what is taken normal and unquestioned in everyday life. But the point to me is that these can *only* be changed actively (i.e., not just by some accident or structural change in the environment/world) through own, or via others' agency.

Now, having said this, I want to get into why I believe we are in hard times for this kind of agency. I worry that human agency may be in crisis, that we lose the capability to act on our own behalf, think intentionally, what it is that we truly want to do, and then, being able to act on this intention.

A crisis of human agency may lie particularly in two, interlinked aspects: the erosion both of the capability to really conceive intentional action, and of the capability to (collectively) perform it. This I want to explore and elaborate in the following, while also reflecting in a later stage on the issues of change in relation to the societal challenges we have to deal with, which, in my view, particularly becomes increasingly hard due to a deep and sustained loss of collective agency.

The mechanisms I worry about here in this essay are more recent and are largely linked to novel technological and economic developments. While there is also a necessity to look at general human traits of inaction with regards to needed societal change (such as that it is usually comfortable to remain in the status quo, that we cannot care about everything, or that there is also an issue with conformity and compliance), my focus here is really more on recent developments adding on top.

Why us?

Before doing so, I want to quickly clarify my general usage of 'we' and 'us' in this article. Thinking about agency on this general level in the context of societal change combined with using 'we' throughout the article, runs the risk of implicating to some readers, that I believe we are all equally responsible to take action, and should all individually change (falling into a common 'neoliberal'-narrative), or that I want to insinuate that 'we' are a homogenous group all having the same values and we are just too troubled to act. It is more the case that I want to emphasize the principal possibility of initiating and enacting change on a personal, very individual level, which to me is crucial to have a possibility to get something moving. I try to break down what I mean: let's for simplicity assume that only a few powerful people are responsible for a

³ Much literature along the lines of Weber, Giddens, Archer, Bhaskar, Bourdieu, Bandura, Sen, Nussbaum, Sewell, or Latour, to name a few, has done so, particularly in sociological or psychological terms. For more philosophical and fundamental discussions, I suggest to consult *The Routledge Handbook of Philosophy of Agency*, edited by Luca Ferrero (2021).

certain issue. Their agency would be crucial, but for some reason, they don't act accordingly. Maybe out of self-interest, or because they are ill-informed, or because they may not have the necessary agency in the first place. Then, however, it is the responsibility of other people, who realize this, to challenge these agents responsible and in power. And here again, we can ask, but who are these people to challenge? It can be people in the surroundings of the powerful and responsible, but it may also be people on the streets. And even if it is not clear, how to convince or challenge whom, who then again can do something in the higher level of some hierarchy, and so on, with all the complexity involved, it is crucial to not deny, that, in principle, such pathways exist. And this pathway can start, I believe, with any individual who mobilizes other individuals to really have an impact by (collective) agency. In this sense, the 'we' is meant as being inclusive, that we all can try to initiate or be part of such a pathway of change, without ever meaning to suggest that it is ultimately an equal burden that we all carry. Because it is not, power brings different responsibility.

2. Agency under Systematic Attack

The digital revolution, in intricate combination with globalized hyper-capitalism, has changed and is still changing our lives fundamentally, our being in a sense, with all the shifted and novel environments we suddenly find ourselves in. These changed environments, I believe, make agency more and more challenging every day. It boils down to the downsides of recent technology and their broad adoption, which then our economic systems have exacerbated, without us having agentically been able to anticipate and do something about such forceful effects.

The Attention Economy

Putting it simply, since scarcity of many needed and wished-for goods in large parts of the world has vanished, more and more effort has been put on selling products which, in their essence, are actually abundantly available: from the most recent processed food novelty, over ever-changing trends in fashion, to the newest 'smart' devices. This abundance of products and the need to sell them led to a persistently escalating attention-competition process; by pursuing people, their conscious and subconscious being, in more and more intricate, but total ways.

This process is recently guided and nurtured by a profoundly psychologically informed processing of our massively collected and shared personal data, targeting people highly specifically via tailored forms of advertisements. While this process has in principle a long history (e.g., [Smith, 1956](#); [Turow, 2011](#)) – some form of data has always been considered to make target-group-oriented advertisement – a recent qualitative leap of the attention economies' totality appeared particularly with the invention and capitalization of social media in the late 2000s and early 2010s, further escalated by the abundant adoption of smartphones. Not only are we more reachable by advertisement, but the advertisement also gets more and more effective with increased personalization, possible due to the power lying in big data and the algorithms that process and analyze it. This advertisement is not only about selling products, but also about selling narratives and having influence. What direct political consequences this can have came to public awareness probably with the case of Cambridge Analytica in relation to discussions around Brexit or the first election of Trump (see [Kaiser, 2019](#)).

Through the emergence of the digital space and its expansion to our daily lives, people can hardly hide from the pull: advertisement and entertainment both are ever-presently and societally linked to our hands and heads. Since in over-saturated capitalist societies every enterprise has to take such measures in order to sell their products and survive in the market, this attention economy emerged as a logical systemic consequence, which pulls and pulls on us everywhere, the enterprises winning with the most intricate and persistent grasp of our attention (hence, the escalation of the process).

How this specifically affects our agency is quite intuitively clear: This ever-present pull intrudes our consciousness and shapes our experience and doing substantially, and it becomes harder and harder to individually escape. All day long, we are told in most intricate ways what to desire and what we should buy, making it increasingly challenging for the human being to reflect on their own, more guardedly, what they want and what they intend to do. The conception of intentional action, thinking about what we actually want to do, is through this not only subdued, because we are unable to consciously reflect on our goals and desires, but more so, actively shaped.

The Digital Space and Social Media

As part of the escalating process just described, the emergence of the digital space and social media has been crucial. The digital space became a medium for most of the dynamics described here. As most of us are well aware, the digital space has the characteristic to lure us in, into an often social, but largely technologically mediated realm. I guess much of the lure comes due to the interlinkage of the attention economy and new forms of entertainment, as hinted at already above.

The digital space enabled the economy to seek out our attention in novel ways. Social media played a key role in this, a development that was only possible through people's proactive and intense contributions. In this sense, the attention economy has increasingly incorporated its advertising forces into the social fabric — it seems that everyone wants to sell you something now — by creating new jobs such as influencers, which not only couple entertainment and advertising in novel ways, but also, in a sense, “democratize” this dynamic, as anyone can become an influencer and earn money through advertising by depicting a persona in the digital space.

However, this development unleashed a novel dynamic: advertising increasingly seeks us out *socially*, thus, suddenly became highly parasocial. Driven by a growing number of individuals aspiring to monetize the production and marketing of their creations, attention becomes the central currency, as pay and legitimacy are derived from clicks, watch time, and user engagement. Consequently, people who incorporate these new forms of advertising-based entertainment increasingly compete for our attention.

It does not help that the algorithms social media is based on, of course, elevate this logic. Apps are designed to make us spend as much time as possible on them, so they have our attention to sell exactly these. The more addictive these apps are, and hence the more reliably time is spent on them, the better they are financially for the respective enterprise. This often coincides with different modes of attention-grabbing, specifically eliciting central emotions such as anger or fear. This, as Joe Folley (2025) has argued in a video essay, may drastically reduce our ability to think and engage

with others critically. It is rather clear that having the time, mental ability, and resources to think and reflect critically is crucial to building individual and collective agency, since it is needed to conceive reasonable goals and actionable (collective) pathways to achieve these.

And all these sophisticated but, in consequence cognitively and emotionally tiring efforts to get our attention became a part of social life for most people. We are putting ourselves out there, without much protection, in the storm of continuous efforts of attention-grabbing and seeking. However, a somewhat uninterrupted attention would exactly be needed, for deep engagement with the world, other people, and oneself, to reflect on deep desires and meaning, as well as possible ways to act accordingly. What happens to our agency in such an environment?

Old & New Addictions

The issue of the capitalization of addictive behaviours has been mentioned earlier already. Becoming addicted to a certain product, drug or behaviour appears strongly related to a substantial shift, and arguably, loss of agency.⁴ An addicted person does have limited control, particularly over the performance of addictive behaviour. While this inherently limits agency at least to some degree with regards to the addiction, furthermore, addictions often affect times larger parts of the doings and life of the addicted person. The moment a person feels deeply forced to do a certain thing, may it be consuming drugs, gambling, scrolling through social media for hours or buying products the person doesn't need, agency is limited. While always a degree, the relationship is rather clear: the less addicted, meaning here, the less forced a person feels to act in a certain way, the more agency the person has in this regard specifically, but also the more agency the person may have in general, because they may have more time, energy and resources to think about and do other things, than dealing with their own addictions.

However, now we are in a situation where a large part of our economic system, 'limbic capitalism' (Courtwright, 2019)⁵, capitalizes on and therefore even encourages the emergence of certain addictions. Combined with new technological means, sources of addictions became ever-present, available via a grab into our pocket and some swipes on a screen. Most people can reach within seconds, or be reached by, the digital space. This comes with the ever-presence of a multitude of different addictive temptations: all sorts of shopping opportunities, entertainment, social media, online casinos or porn are all available at people's, and often times children's, instant disposal.

Addictions are incredibly challenging to act against, because they shape people's actions through complex and encapsulating forces. The addicted individual is, in terms of their addiction, not an agentic one, but in a way governed, controlled even.

⁴ The link between addiction and agency is both theoretically and empirically quite challenging, and always depends on the specific case and addiction with regards to quality and extend. For a nuanced discussion, see Clarke-Doanne and Tabb (2022).

⁵ Courtwright (2019) describes limbic capitalism as a "technologically advanced but socially regressive business system in which global industries, often with the help of complicit governments and criminal organizations, encourage excessive consumption and addiction" (p. 6).

LLMs & AI

A quite recent development is the broad utilization of generative artificial intelligence, usually in the form of asking large language models (LLMs) for support in (often times somewhat creative) tasks, that earlier would have been solely a human responsibility (see [Bick et al., 2024](#); [Skjuve et al., 2024](#)). These ongoing developments – and no one knows where it exactly goes, whether also the emergence of artificial general intelligence (AGI) is about to happen – pose intricate challenges for our own human agency. While the crises mentioned so far attack more our attention and awareness itself, the emergence of AI is shaping us in very different ways.

But before writing down my own thoughts on how AI interferes with human agency, out of curiosity, I thought I will ask two of these models myself. When I ask ChatGPT 5.2 and DeepSeek 3.2 to give two sentences about AI and human agency interference, it produces⁶:

“Generative AI can interfere with human agency by subtly shifting decision-making, creativity, and judgment from humans to algorithmic systems that optimize for efficiency, engagement, or probability rather than human intentions or values. When AI-generated suggestions, texts, or images increasingly pre-structure choices, they risk narrowing the space for reflective deliberation and making human action more reactive, dependent, and less consciously intentional.”
(ChatGPT 5.2, normal chat)

“Generative AI can interfere with human agency by shifting decision-making, creativity, and judgment from humans to automated systems, thereby reducing individuals’ sense of authorship and responsibility for outcomes. When people increasingly rely on AI-generated suggestions or content, their choices may be subtly guided or constrained by opaque models, weakening reflective autonomy and critical engagement.”
(ChatGPT 5.2, temporary chat)

“Generative AI can subtly constrain human agency by shaping choices through curated suggestions and pre-fabricated content, narrowing the horizon of original thought and action. Furthermore, by outsourcing tasks like writing, designing, and decision-making to algorithms, it risks eroding the essential human capacity for judgment, intentionality, and authentic creation.”
(DeepSeek 3.2, normal chat, empty account)

To be honest, I think all replies offer quite substantial material to think about. Of course, the first reply seems even more elaborate to me, since it seems to draw on my understanding of agency, which I shared with the system while language editing my previous work over the years, whereas blank ChatGPT's or DeepSeek's reply seems to draw more from general understandings and debates.

The interesting thing now is that I am tempted to think along the lines of the suggestions of the LLMs. I could critique or elaborate on what ChatGPT or DeepSeek produced here. While I think it touches on some aspects that are crucial, I will suppress the urge to subdue my own ‘creative’ thinking and align it with what the models, very reasonably, suggested. I only want to highlight here that easily reasonable points can be

⁶ I used the following prompt three times, one as part of a normal chat of ChatGPT, so the model could access the text I gave it for language editing my own articles on agency over the years, one as part of a ‘temporary chat’ hence ChatGPT producing irrespective of my data, and one using an empty account in DeepSeek: “Hey ChatGPT [DeepSeek]! I am working on an essay on “Is Human Agency in Crisis?” and I am writing a brief paragraph about generative AI and human agency. I want to ask you the following. “How does generative AI interfere with human agency?” Can you give me a very brief two sentence text for inclusion in my essay? Thank you.”

produced by these models without much effort, and outputs are specific to what data I shared with the model already during the process of having worked with it.

To start my worry, made just self-evident, the utilization of these tools becomes more and more common and their productions even find their way into articles like this one – sometimes with indication, as here, but too often, without (see [Brainard, 2025](#), for alarming trends in academia, and, [Simon et al., 2025](#) for a report in journalism). We see a trend of web articles being increasingly produced by AI, now likely even having surpassed human-produced and uploaded content in November 2024 ([Paredes et al., 2025](#)). There is also the increased worry that in academia, mainly AI-written articles are listed, for example by Google Scholar, next to credible and peer-reviewed sources ([Haider et al., 2024](#)).

In probably more and more areas it is, or it will soon be, expected to use these tools for many tasks. There may actually be a strong comparative disadvantage a person may have if they're not using AI in certain job environments or even somewhat creative endeavours, because it is often just seemingly quicker, easier, and also largely free of charge than to rely on other human beings or on your own abilities and effort. It is not difficult to imagine a society where people socially are expected to use it.

I believe the main issue with AI with regards to our agency is the following, structured in two distinct points: 1) the usage of AI as a first step in the creative thinking and work-process becomes standard, implicating all sorts of potential influence, misinformation and creative limitations, and, 2) the learning process is hindered, particularly for young people – it is harder to acquire the type of skills the AI is offering, and so less and less people will be able to transcend the AI's capabilities in some regards.

The first, the default to inquire with generative AI when thinking about something, shapes agency by changing the process of creatively conceiving actions. There is a risk that this inquiry will be more and more standardized, externally influenced or guided by misinformation/hallucinations via the pathway of 'consulting' an AI. However, even if AI were accurate and highly creative, or the process would enable humans to interact highly creatively in cooperation with AI, the process is at risk to lead to humans losing their individual capability to be creative independently. Preliminary evidence suggests precisely this: while a creative co-production process with generative AI may lead to individually highly creative outputs ([Shaer et al., 2024](#); [Sun et al., 2025](#)), some experimental trials indicate simultaneously the loss of independent creativity (i.e., being creative without AI) as a consequence of AI consultancy ([Kumar et al., 2025](#)). Additionally, while the individually co-created creative results may be impressive to evaluators, there are good reasons that we may lose a "collective diversity of novel content" ([Doshi & Hauser, 2024](#), p. 1). However, this is a quickly changing field, and we don't know how generative AI and 'its creativity'⁷ develops (see [Franceschelli & Musolesi, 2025](#), on assessing the creativity of AI).

Second, the learning issue will throughout the years, procedurally erode the agency of people because in many regards they may just not have learned the abilities that can constitute their agency (i.e., their abilities, such as lying in competencies and skills). Also, there is the issue of societal assessment of these skills, because most term papers,

⁷ Of course the creativity of an AI is not necessarily its own, since it draws on the (largely human) data it has been trained on as well as what is available to it in the digital space.

etc. can be quite easily written now already without highly sophisticated prompting by LLMs. If we are not forced to do certain things, like thinking about something in a structured way without help, or learning how to write or think critically, then we may not really learn it. We may always rely on an AI. And while this is not inherently a problematic thing, and also not totally new in an abstract sense, we often rely on other entities, usually humans, to do certain things – the ready-hand nature of AI may just substantially change how and if we learn certain things. What should also be mentioned is, that the rise of something that could be called AI-agency (e.g., AI agents interacting with us on social media, sometimes seemingly as humans) coincides with the other forces potentially diminishing human agency mentioned above.

Regarding the interaction of human agency and AI, I am not entirely sure in which direction it plays out. I could imagine a profound case to be made for AI actually to increase the agency of people. However, this could only be the case, if we truly learn to properly deal with generative AI individually as well as societally. It also depends on the nature of these models, or later on, general AI. In how far we can (and want) to control or shape it. However, having said that, there appears good reason, as just sketched, for me to be here a bit more on the sceptic side, paradoxically, also considering the other issues the ChatGPT and DeepSeek 'mentioned', such as the intricate interweaving of AI algorithms and decision-making with human agency. It appears likely to me, that the pull of the development draws AI agency to substantially replace and diminish human agency, if we don't do something profoundly against it.

Individualization & Loneliness

A quite different issue, which may have detrimental effects, particularly on collective agency, is the apparent and concerning development of individualization and loneliness. Studies have found a substantial prevalence of pathologic loneliness symptoms across the globe, varying between countries ([Surkalim et al., 2022](#)), as well as increasing feelings of loneliness in the last decades, particularly in emerging adults ([Buecker et al., 2021](#)). Feeling and being lonely shapes both the individual as well as collective agency in troubling ways. Reasons for this increased loneliness and individualization (and I see them linked) are diverse, but there is likely a connection to the emergence of the digital space and the novel options of parasocial relationships. Studies have found at least a correlational link between loneliness and social media usage ([O'Day & Heimberg, 2021](#)).

I come to believe that particularly loneliness is a threat to human agency in two ways. First, if we feel or factually are disconnected to other people, then many actions are simply 'unavailable' to us. We may not have friends to talk to and reflect together on what to do about a certain thing, or what goals to achieve. Here then, also, parasocial relationships or the usage of generative AI is likely to fill the gap. But we need humans to orient ourselves. Also, our very own capability to do certain things, requires also the capability to motivate other people to join in. Many actions, even if individually initiated, are collective actions.

More crucially, in a highly individualized world, where many people feel alone, trying to soothe the symptoms with social media or artificial companions, collective human agency seems increasingly challenging. But it would be exactly this what is necessary: initiating and enacting shared endeavours, trying to change something, to face the unfolding human crises we otherwise cannot escape.

I have the impression that even though the internet gave us plenty of new ways to connect in principle, novel economy-driven algorithms leave us deeply disconnected. If people are feeling increasingly alone, and at the same time, became highly individualized, meaning they mainly correspond to their own interests (and the algorithms of the digital space may encourage this), it is challenging to transcend these and organize collectively for a greater, shared good. However, our societies require such forms of organization to initiate and enact change. If we lose our ability to connect and take action for a shared, complex and large-scale endeavour, then we are either stuck on our structurally given pathway, or follow our individualized goals, lacking the power to actually achieve anything that goes beyond the simple and singular.

3. Towards Finding Agency

So, what to do about this? I probably have painted quite a pessimistic panorama of the situation we and our minds are in. This picture is selective. More positive aspects of some of the mentioned developments could probably be highlighted as well; such as all the knowledge that got readily available, as well as the potential to connect and organize through the digital space, or the enabling potential of generative AI. However, in the end, I also hold the firm belief that the reader, who is, as I am, an affected person by these novel environments, has firsthand experience and can, hopefully, reflect on the title question personally: Is my agency in crisis? And what about my friends and family?

We have to find ways to deal with this ever-changing society we find ourselves in, which we simultaneously can, and – with view to the current societal challenges – have to attempt to change in turn, particularly if we are in positions of power, influence or simply where a change of action matters.

I am also afraid that I have, next to the many positive counter sides I did not really talk about, also omitted some other substantial issues increasingly limiting human agency. One that probably many have firsthand experiences on too, is the increasing complexity of systems and interdependences, as well as related rules and bureaucracies. Such structures, and the related cultures of routine, hinder and always have hindered agency (which is not necessarily a bad thing, because it also protects from injustices as well as harmful, destructive or immoral agency). However, it seems the longer systems exist, the more specialized and complex they become. And furthermore, the harder it is for the agent to not end up in a Kafkaesque labyrinth of regulations, finding no way out, to actually do something, beyond what the system constitutes already.

It is not so easy and requires a lot of knowledge, determination and organizational skills to change established bureaucracies, particularly in liberal democratic systems. The same holds true for making new rules to deal with the issues mentioned in this essay. It is no easy undertaking to do something against the attention economies' pull, the ever-present sources of addictions and distraction, or the abundance and intensifying attempts to innovate generative AI even further. We need strong agentic and collective attempts of people to do something about these issues, as much as we need to do something about the challenges of humankind. This is nothing new, but the reflection offered in this essay may motivate some new perspective on why it feels and is so difficult to do something.

I cannot offer much regarding how to improve the situation, but immediately it is clear that we have to 'look out for' our awareness and attention. It does not surprise, but we have to be *mindful* of how we engage with the digital space and AI, use its potentials wisely, and also stay alert on how our attention is grabbed and psychologically chained to products, entertainment and addictive behaviours. Beyond protecting our attention, it is also crucial to think critically about what we can do specifically in the very position we are in. What is my pathway of initiating or contributing to the change I want to see, that I also may be responsible for? There should be no illusions; every person is in a different position and has different means to act. The baker at the street corner may not need to, or have the means to change the world (further) and also does not have the responsibility to do so. But what means and responsibility does a manager, a politician, a banker or a researcher have in their very situation? These questions have to be individually addressed, to see from the individuals' perspectives where moments of agency can lie to contribute to deal with the societal challenges we have to face.

Furthermore, we have to nurture our agency by learning again how to build and sustain real connection, not only to feel less lonely, but also since it can easily be the basis for starting collective attempts of change. The missing link from individual agency to change is actually collective agency, where we manage to organize, to challenge established ways of doing and established power structures. How is this actually achieved? I think we need to understand better, more clearly and directly how human-led, purposeful change comes about on a collective and impactful level. Many people are trying things out, and diverse disciplines such as social movement, organization or sustainability transformation studies deal partially exactly with such questions.

The role of research is crucial in this. Diverse research endeavours have to better understand the mechanisms of novel techno-capitalist environments on agency, as suggested here. But crucially, with regards to world-wide human challenges, such as climate change, environmental deterioration, or the destructive tendencies of our (financial) economies, research has to examine agentic pathways of change more explicitly, while simultaneously taking the perspectives of the agents involved with their limited human agency, and seeking productive strategies of how to foster change agency within these specific contexts. Research has to understand clearer how the change, appearing from a scientific and political consensus necessary, can be agentially made. We cannot shy away from dealing with change agency directly. We don't understand well how to rescue our agency, how to wake up, and build and utilize the change agency needed. Of course, this is all related to power dynamics too, which have been left rather unaddressed in this essay. Powerful agents often hinder systematically the change of the very systems that may sustain their power, which, however, actually would need change. This reinforces the looming crises out of ignorant self-interest, but the truth is also that there is only the way to challenge these reproducing powerful systems by utilizing our individual and collective agency, if there is any left.

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Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT 5.2 in order to improve the language and flow of this article. Whenever using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the suggested content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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